

Can the acts of ISIS against the Yazidi population in Iraq be constituted as a genocide?

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Abstract

This paper examines the atrocities committed by the Islamic State (ISIS) against the Yazidi minority in Northern Iraq during 2014, with a particular focus on the Sinjar massacre. Established as a self-proclaimed caliphate by Sunni militants, ISIS sought to revive a puritanical version of Islamic governance through violence, conquest, and the suppression of minority groups. Drawing on academic literature, human rights reports, and media coverage, this study investigates whether the actions of ISIS in Sinjar meet the legal and moral criteria of genocide. Evidence demonstrates systematic efforts to annihilate the Yazidi population through mass executions, forced conversions, child soldier recruitment, and the organized sexual enslavement of women and girls. These actions reflect an intentional plan to destroy the Yazidi community's social, cultural, and physical existence. The paper concludes that the crimes perpetrated by ISIS constitute genocide under international law, emphasizing the importance of justice, accountability, and long-term reintegration for survivors.

1.0 Introduction

The Islamic State was created as a self-proclaimed caliphate by the Sunni militant who use Islam to foster the International holy war (Nuruzzaman 2015:2-3). ISIS poses a threat both to the Middle East, where the majority of its military operations is located and to the West, where it seeks to shake the politics of the global order (Nuruzzaman 2015:2-3). Many young people left their Western homes to join the Islamic State, as fighters or wives of fighters (Antunez 2016:1). The caliphate was originally established in Iraq and Syria. The ultimate plan was to re-establish the plan used by the Ottoman Empire and spread the caliphate to Europe (Antunez 2016:2-7). Day to day life in the Islamic State was controlled under the strict Sharia law, which originated in the 8th century AD (Antunez 2016:2-7). After conquering parts of Iraq and Syria, the social structure of the state was modified in a way that served the holy war's purpose. Led by the thoughts of a Sunni pure society, who mirrored the society from ancient times (Antunez 2016:2-7), ISIS carried out the attacks against humanity.

In August 2014, ISIS and its fighters set to conquer the Sinjar region of Iraq and to especially target the Yazidi minority that lived there. Records show that the region around Mount Sinjar is home to the majority of the world's Yazidi population (Human Rights Council 2016:1). The attack resulted in thousands of Yazidis being displaced in neighboring countries or even in the European Union's states (Paraszczuk 2015). Those who were unable to escape suffered a terrible faith. Roughly estimated 10,000 people belonging to the Yazidi community never managed to escape the initial attack (Rukmini 2015). This paper will outline the events of the Sinjar massacre as well as subsequent events happening to those involved in the conflict, to clarify whether the gathered evidence can proclaim atrocities against Yazidis as genocide. To bring light to the opinions and reports, both academic papers and newspaper publications is used in this paper.

2.0 Definition of genocide

Many definitions of genocide have been proposed since 1959 (Jones 2017:23). There are a few common definition points that thread through all the conceptualizations. Genocide is a deliberate act committed by people in power who seek to exterminate members of a certain group or population, based solely on their membership in that group (Jones 2017:23-24). One of the most comprehensive

definitions of genocide is by Jack Nusan Porter from 1982, which is as following:

“Genocide is the deliberate destruction, in whole or in part, by a government or its agents, of a racial, sexual, religious, tribal or political minority. It can involve not only mass murder, but also starvation, forced deportation, and political, economic and biological subjugation. Genocide involves three major components: ideology, technology, and bureaucracy/organization.” (Jones 2017:24)

Some of the other definitions also emphasize the point when the members of the weaker group are prevented to have children or when their children are taken away to be integrated into another group (Jones 2017:25). But one of the most recognizable features of genocide is that it is tainted with murder or synonymous with mass killings and liquidation of people (Jones 2017:26-27). However, the political or law-abiding background to the mass killings is less obligatory as a definition point (Jones 2017:23-27) because genocide can often occur between religious groups without the formal backing of the group in power, where it can even be denied for a long time, e.g. mass murder of an entire city’s Muslim men and boys in Bosnia (Jones 2017:65). When talking about colonial and imperial genocides, the focus has always remained on the destruction of indigenous people (Jones 2017:65), whose faith was to vanish or become so weak or isolated to be disabled to claim any power. Jones (2017:253) also emphasizes cases where entire populations were deliberately tortured, e.g. the genocide over the Yazidi population during ISIS.

In respect to legal implementation of the genocide definition of the Genocide Convention, rape and sexual violence which are part of Article II came to a lot of vagueness, especially what does causing serious harm actually stand for, the need to prove and provide evidence for an objective requirement for the act of genocide, and the need to view sexual violence just as a tool to prevent births in a group suffering the atrocities in order to fall under the umbrella of genocide (Pecorella 2015:945). Other definitions emphasize that genocide is a broader term than its legal definition or interpretation and that it should be considered in respect to the historical memory of a group (Ferreira 2013:5). Looked in this light, genocide is merely the partial elimination of a national group (Ferreira 2013:5). Some sources of genocide can be ideological often based in some form of ethnic cleanliness, such as the theory of the Aryan race in Germany, the theory of Great Serbia in Serbia, and more recently the ISIL atrocities of the Yazidi population (Peltola:145-147).

2.1 Background to the massacre

The Islamic State of Iraq and Levant, born from Al Qaeda, became worldwide news when it occupied one-third of Iraq and half of Syria, a territory which they proclaimed to be a caliphate, hoping to revoke the glory of the Ottoman Empire and other rabic autocracies historically existing in the Middle East and North Africa (Rukmini and Falih 2019). This Islamic caliphate incorporated a strict fundamental Islamic Shari'a law (Jäger m.fl. 2019:1), a practice known for medieval punishments such as stoning to death for adultery or cutting the arm for stealing, which was extensively practised. However, as will be explained later in this text, ISIS bent the law to its' needs to recruit soldiers from the area as well as abroad. The self-proclaimed caliph of ISIL, Abu Bakr al-Baghdadi, traced his ancestry to the daughter of the prophet Muhammed, which gave him leverage to lead the caliphate by ruling over the existing inhabitants of the region, as well as importing population from all over the world (Rukmini and Falih 2019). The northern territory of this caliphate, the mountains of Sinjar, up to that point was largely inhabited by a minority population of Yazdi (Rukmini and Falih 2019). Yazidis are one small minority in Iraq, whos predecessors are thought to share Kurdish descent (Smith 2014). They believe in one supreme being, and their religion has been dated back to the pre-Islamic period (Smith 2014). Although their religion is based on Christianity, Judaism and Zoroastrianism, their faith is looked upon as a sect, devil-worship and other views that caused persecution of the Yazidi population throughout history (Smith 2014).

A few weeks after the creation of a caliphate, Yazidi women and girls were kidnapped from their homes and brought to a building in Raqqa, which served as a something between a shop and a red light district from which those women were enslaved (Rukmini and Falih 2019). It is important to note that these enslavements happened in a preplanned and strategic way right after the occupation of the Northern Iraqi territory by ISIS (Rukmini 2015). According to the survivors' account reported by the New York Times (Rukmini 2015), men and women were separated immediately after capture; estimated 5,000 men and boys were taken away and murdered, but the girls and women were transported and held in confinement before being sold off as sex slaves to Islamic State fighters in Iraq and Syria. The Islamic State allowed this sex trade as legal and allowed by the Islamic religion, because the slaves in questions, Yazidi minority, were unbelievers, and therefore less than Muslim, Christian, or Jewish communities mentioned in Q'uran (Rukmini 2015)

2.2 Destruction of the Yazidi community

The 'Sinjar massacre' involved many elements of genocide, including mass killings, prosecution, displacement, forced conversion to Islam, and what is most prominent, these experiences were gender-specific (Jäger m.fl. 2019:1-2). Thousands of men were killed and thousands of women and children were kept in captivity. They suffered acts of brutality aimed to destroy the whole Yazidi community, through something that's been called 'religious cleansing' of people and territory (Jäger m.fl. 2019:2-5). Women were forced into sex-trade, men were forced to convert to Islam or suffer extermination, and young boys were converted into child soldiers for the ISIL cause (Jäger m.fl. 2019:2,7).

The Yazidis are known to practise their ancient religion and their estimated population is 1.5 million, residing in Iraq, Syria, Turkey, and Armenia (Cetorelli m.fl. 2017:3). Before the atrocities, it was estimated that around 400,000 Yazidi's lived in the region of Sinjar, based on data provided by Kurdish officials and The United Nations (Cetorelli m.fl. 2017:1). During Saddam Hussein's rule, Yazidis were the most disadvantaged community, marginalized and neglected, and in 2014 they were the easiest target of Sunni extremists, who organized an attack and a siege as members of the Islamic State (Cetorelli m.fl. 2017:3).

Chronologically, the siege of Mount Sinjar on 4 August left a large number of Yazidis stranded from basic human necessities such as: water, food and shelter in the heat of summer (+ 50°C) (Cetorelli m.fl. 2017:3). A few days later, an organized intervention of the Iraqi government, the United States airstrikes and humanitarian aid airdrops, as well as helicopter rescue missions, led to a corridor opened by Kurdish forces (Cetorelli m.fl. 2017:3). The majority of Yazidis, an estimated 300,000, fled across Syria to finally reach the Kurdistan Region of Iraq, where they were treated as refugees (Cetorelli m.fl. 2017:3).

When analyzing the extent of the genocide, (Cetorelli m.fl. 2017:1-2) looked at each demographic separately, children and adults, and male and female, after which they concluded that 2.5% of the Yazidi population was killed or kidnapped in August 2014. Viewed in numbers, this is around 10,000 people. During the initial attack men and boys were separated from women in a school, where women and small children were detained on the first floor and men and boys on the ground floor (Human Rights Council 2016:8). Witnesses say that men and boys were taken away and that

their faith is still unknown (Human Rights Council 2016:8). At the beginning stages of the ISIS siege, a third of Yazidis were executed, shot, throat cut or burned alive (Cetorelli m.fl. 2017:1-2). Those who did not suffer the immediate fate died from starvation, injuries or dehydration on Mount Sinjar, and it is estimated that this group was more than 93% children (Cetorelli m.fl. 2017:1-2). Almost 7,000 people were estimated to be kidnapped, thus tortured, sex-traded or subjected to forced religious conversion (Cetorelli m.fl. 2017:1-2). When counting those who managed to escape, less than 20% were children, but the authors state caution to all the data because the situation is ongoing and there are still a lot of people missing (Cetorelli m.fl. 2017:1-2).

Even after the liberation of parts of Northern Iraq in 2017, many members of the Yazidi community are not able to return to their homes and prefer to live as asylum seekers in the European Union or Turkey. Not only because of the fear of recurring attacks by the Islamic State militants, but also because they cannot practice their religion freely and because the relationships with the neighboring Islamic population has been strained, because a lot of muslim neighbors communities collaborated with ISIS against the Yazidi communities (Jäger m.fl. 2019:5).

2.3 Treatment of Yazidi's born and unborn children

Sexual violence is at the core of the concept of genocide because it aims to destroy the fundamental social component of a community, and that is family (Jäger m.fl. 2019:6). It destroys not only intimate relationships but also the long-term reproductive capacity of the group (Jäger m.fl. 2019:6). Apart from imposing conditions that bring death to the Yazidi population, ISIS has taken up measures to prevent Yazidi children from being born, as well as the transfer of Yazidi children from their own families to place them with ISIS fighters (Human Rights Council 2016:1). The final aim of this kind of conduct was to cut children from their families beliefs, religious practices and values, which can ultimately destroy and erase young Yazidi's identity (Human Rights Council 2016:1). After the siege, men and older boys were transferred to Tel Afar, Mosul, and Baaj where they were turned into forced workers for ISIS. Their duties were consisted of building, digging trenches, cleaning streets, and taking care of the ISIS cattle (Human Rights Council 2016:9). Since they were forcibly converted to Islam, they were also forced to follow Islamic religious practices, while attempt to escape was punishable by death (Human Rights Council 2016:9). Children separated from their families suffered a different fate based on their sexes, where girls aged nine and above were taken

from their families and sold as sex slaves to members of ISIS in Syria and Iraq. However, boys aged seven and above were taken from their families and sent to ISIS training bases in Syria and Iraq and later they were sent to the frontline as ISIS forces (Human Rights Council 2016:28).

There is an account of a Yazidi boy who was taken by ISIS at the age of nine and returned at the age of twelve, a completely different person (Dozier 2019). After seeing his father and brother killed, he was trained, converted to Islam, witnessed the battlefield, torture and physical punishment, but when a ransom was paid to get him back to his family he continuously tried to run away back to ISIS (Dozier 2019). He had become extremely violent, attempted to kill his sister with a knife, tried to burn the house down, beat his mother and called the household infidels (Dozier 2019). This boy was clearly brainwashed by ISIS, who told him that he was a conqueror, gave him amphetamines in their food, forced him to wear a suicide belt as a form of attack in case the enemy got to close, showed him how to slit a man's throat, cut off limbs etc. (Dozier 2019).

There are reports that ISIS fighters forced Yazidi women and girls to use birth control not to get pregnant (Rukmini 2016). Other were forced to have an abortion to become available for sex again. When being sold further, to another ISIS fighter, women and girls were taken into the hospital to ensure that they were not pregnant (Rukmini 2016). Ultimately, it is estimated that 5% of Yazidi women and girls got pregnant, and some of them gave birth to children who had an ISIS fighter for a father (Rukmini 2016). Recently, the Iraqi constitution demands that children born to ISIS fathers and Yazidi mothers be registered as Muslim and that that registration converts the mother's religion to Islam as well, which has been judged as genocide by the constitution (Dozier 2019).

3.0 Mental problems of Yazidi caused by ISIS

Those who suffered and survived ISIS's genocide suffer from deteriorated health as well as trauma-related symptoms (Jäger m.fl. 2019:7). In 2015, one thousand one hundred Yazidi women and children were brought to Germany as a particularly vulnerable group of people, who were estimated to have significant chances of developing mental health disorders related to traumatic events (Hillebrecht, Zeiss and Bengel 2018:355-366). The concept of care was designed as a step-by step approach while ensuring they had access to the health care system in Germany with a special focus on psychological services (Hillebrecht, Zeiss and Bengel 2018:355-366).

Then it was found that the women were victims of mass rape and that they were also held in

captivity for at least three months by the self-proclaimed Islamic State. Their first mental health assessment was six months after the captivity when they came to Germany. It showed the extent of their deteriorated mental health, including PTSD (78%), depression (63%) and adjustment disorder (2.7%) (Hillebrecht, Zeiss and Bengel 2018:355-366). After a few months, additional mental health problems emerged and the resulting conditions included somatoform disorder (67%), depression (53%), anxiety (39%), dissociation (28%) and PTSD (57%). The general pattern was that the number of disorders, symptoms and severity of mental health problems increased in women who experienced more rape events (Hillebrecht, Zeiss and Bengel 2018:355-366). Some of the PTSD symptoms include flashbacks, psychological distress, feeling detached from others, and feelings of guilt, worthlessness, insomnia, increased alertness etc.

During an internal evaluation of the Free Yezidi Foundation's in Northern Iraq 200 Yezidi women went through before and after assessment of the mental health intervention they've received for the trauma (Womersley and Arikut-Treecce 2019:5-8). The prevalence of PTSD measured before the intervention was 81.25%, with the biggest symptoms being nightmares, insomnia and intrusive thoughts or flashbacks (Womersley and Arikut-Treecce 2019:5-8). Mental health intervention resulted in a decrease of PTSD prevalence to 45%, along with a 74% increase in self-reported well-being. Factors that deteriorated their mental health the most was collective and multiple losses of the community, the captured and missing Yezidis, fear of continuous strikes, anxieties caused by poor living conditions, as well as separations of family members, regardless whether they were taken away or escaped the area seeking refuge (Womersley and Arikut-Treecce 2019:5-8).

3.1 Determining ISIS genocide against Yazidi

On 16 June 2016, The "UN Commission of Inquiry on Syria of the UN Human Rights Council" proclaimed the ISIS violence against Yazidi's as genocide "that has occurred and that is ongoing" (United Nations Human Rights OHCHR 2016). The UN Commission calls upon States' obligations under the Genocide Convention to act immediately to prevent further violence, but most of all to punish genocide (United Nations Human Rights OHCHR 2016). The Commission also urges international recognition of the genocide (United Nations Human Rights OHCHR 2016), that was later recognized in the United States of America, the European Union, Australia, Scotland, Armenia etc.

Although these events base their judgement on the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court that defines elements of genocide (killings, mental and bodily harm, preventing birth, transferring children to other groups), crimes against humanity and war crimes, it seems that finding legal justice in genocide cases is not as simple or obvious as it should be. To start, the United Nations Security Council and the International Criminal Court have no jurisdiction over crimes in Iraq and Syria (Van Schaack 2018:1). That is why the United Nations General Assembly created in 2016 an international, impartial and independent mechanism to assist in the prosecution of persons responsible for crimes under international law since 2011, which requires Syria to cooperate in its work (Van Schaack 2018:1). Unfortunately, Syria has denied the consent or any operation of this body (Van Schaack 2018:1). Iraq is a bit better in this regard because they'd requested assistance from the UN Security Council to establish the international crimes committed by the Islamic State in Iraq and Levant, which led to the creation of the Iraqi Independent Investigations Team (IIIT) (Van Schaack 2018:2).

That being said, it has been shown that legally proving genocidal intent is very difficult (Van Schaack 2018:11). One of the reasons is that it is legally difficult to prove who is responsible, the individual soldier who implemented the plan, the 'general' who ordered it or the state or government who designed a genocidal policy or propaganda (Van Schaack 2018:11). The difficulty to make conclusive findings can be most clearly seen in the work of The International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia (ICTY) (Van Schaack 2018:12). The Tribunal first concluded that a person participating in genocide cannot be proclaimed not responsible because he selected only a few of the minority group members to kill, and let others live, because it does show genocidal intent (Van Schaack 2018:12). However, the Tribunal shocked the world when it ruled in 2007. that Serbia wasn't responsible for genocide in Srebrenica. In 2017. it has restated its judgement that the mass killings in Srebrenica in 1995 constituted a genocide, and convicted the military commander Ratko Mladic. Moreover, The Dutch Supreme Court upheld a ruling that Dutch UN peacekeepers had failed to protect 350 people in Bosnia in 1995. but also ruled that the Dutch government be 10% responsible for the atrocity.

One of the challenges that the Iraqi judicial system is facing is the lack of procedures and infrastructure for such cases where the victims are highly sensitive and vulnerable, such as informed

consent to participate in the trial on their own, and not be controlled by male family members (Van Schaack 2018:29). One more problem is an inadequate witness protection program which doesn't allow the victims and witnesses to testify remotely or with devices that change the voice, and to completely mask her or his identity from public records (Van Schaack 2018:29). It is feared that because of this conditions many women would refuse to testify to protect their identity. This is the only thing that allows them to continue with their lives. Besides, no mechanism offers psychological support to victims going into the trials, which can make that victim an easy target for the defence (Van Schaack 2018:29).

4.0 Conclusion

To conclude, crimes committed by the Islamic State in Northern Iraq in 2014, have been classified as genocide against Yazidi people by the United Nations and many parliaments across the world. Yazidi, an Iraqi minority has been recognized as an easy unprotected target for Sunni militant extremists. There are some undeniable elements in the events that prove the conduct of ISIS towards Yazidi's was aimed at leading the whole community to silent death, disappearance and destruction. First is the separation of men and women, and the subsequent execution of most men. Then there is conversion to Islam as well as the separation of boys from their families to be trained as ISIS fighters, while they were in fact child soldiers.

The prominent element of genocide is the organized sex trade of the Yazidi women and girls, which incorporated all the elements of extermination. These are preventing birth, causing bodily harm, destroying the core family values of the minority group, and causing mental and physical health problems to the victims. While the attempt to destroy, dehumanize and erase the Yazidi community led to around 10,000 immediate victims, the prosecution of ISIS fighters for their atrocities remains to be seen. There may be some slight hope that Iraq will prosecute those responsible for the genocide, but the situation in Syria remains open largely because of the lack of cooperation between the international community and the Syrian government.

Even though trials and justice may take decades, the historical value of condemning genocide is well worth the wait, not just for the victims and their families, but for the international community as well. The other long term process that remains to be thoroughly addressed is the re integration of traumatised, ashamed or brainwashed Yazidi members, who have to reinstall their

values in broken social and moral structures of their community. Since many Yazidi's now live abroad, it is questionable to what extent this remains possible. However, Yazidi is a minority who have survived many attacks during history, and they are still here.

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